

Faculty of Veterinary Medicine
University of Tehran

Iranian Veterinary Surgery
Association

Veterinary Surgery (ISVS)

The 13th Iranian Symposium of

Veterinary Surgery, Anesthesia and Diagnostic Imaging (ISVSAD)

A Dystocia Due to Pelvic Fracture in a Golden Rottweiler: Clinical Report

Abdolhamid Meimandi Parizi¹, Asghar Mogheiseh¹, Arghavan Mofidi*²

¹ Department of Clinical Sciences, School of Veterinary Medicine, Shiraz University, Shiraz, Iran.

² Resident of Veterinary Surgery, Department of Clinical Sciences, School of Veterinary Medicine, Shiraz University, Shiraz, Iran.

Email: Mofidi.arghavan@gmail.com

CR109

Case Description- An 18 month old Golden Rottweiler dog was referred to Veterinary Hospital of Shiraz University, with a history of two days suffering from dystocia and a pelvic fracture was treated six month ago.

Clinical Finding- In general examination the vital signs were in normal ranges. Dehydration was obvious. There were discharge of green liquid with stinking smell. In palpation one fetus was stuck in brith canal that was hardly withdrawn. Ultrasonography showed that all fetuses were dead.

Treatment and Outcome- According to animal condition the patient was immediately prepared for caesarean section. Sedation was done with Acepromazine and induction with Ketamine and Midazolam. Hence, caesarean section was performed and retrieved six dead pups. Despite the advice of the surgeon for OHE, the owner was not in agreement. Administrations of Oxytocin and systemic antibiotics Cefazolin with Flunixin were post-operative procedures in 5 days.

Clinical Relevance- Dystocia is defined as difficult brith or the inability to expel the fetus through the brith canal without assistance¹. One of the reasons for dystocia is pelvic fracture, in some cases the pelvic didn't have enough flexibility and dystocia has been probable. The normal vaginal discharge at parturition is a dark green color; abnormal color or character warrants immediate attention². It is important before operation the animal should become stable with adequate fluid, corticosteroid and antibiotics.

Key Words: Dystocia, Caesarean section, Pelvic fracture, Golden Rottweiler, Dog.

References

1. Forsberg CL, Persson G. A survey of dystocia in the Boxer breed. *Acta Vet Scand* 2007; 49(1): 8.
2. Jackson P. Dystocia in the dog and cat. In: *Handbook of Veterinary Obstetrics*. 2nd ed. WB Saunders, Oxford, 2004; 141-166

